

Synthesis, characterization and mesomorphic investigation of 1,3,5-trisubstituted pyrazole terminal group based liquid crystalline compounds

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Abstract: A new homologous series of 1,3,5-tri substituted pyrazole derivatives derived from 3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-5-(4H) one, Alkoxy benzoyl chloride, 4n- alkoxy Aniline have been synthesized, viz. 4-[(4-n-alkoxyphenyl)(4-n-octyloxyphenylimino)methyl]-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazole-5-(4H)one. The compounds of this series have been characterized by elemental analysis, FT-IR, 1H-NMR, UV Spectroscopy methods. The liquid crystalline properties have been investigated by POM (Polarising optical microscopy) and DSC studies. All the derivatives are mesomorphic in nature showing nematic and smectic phase. The use of phenyl substituted pyrazole core has a very dramatic effect on the melting clearing points. The mesomorphic nature has been analysed in terms of structure property relationship.

Keywords: mesophase, nematic phase, smectic phase, schiff base, trisubstituted pyrazole.

Introduction

The detailed study of many mesogenic homologous series has helped to evolve some general rules for the effect of chemical constitution in the nematogenic and smectogenic compounds [1]. There have been a variety of compounds reported with liquid crystalline properties, but heterocyclic moieties less explored, compared to homocyclic moieties [2]. Furthermore heteroatoms offer the possibility of several modes of co-ordination. Thermotropic liquid crystals are of great technological importance [3-5]. Many series of liquid crystalline compounds containing heterocyclic groups have been synthesized because of their interesting properties [6]. Various mesomorphic heterocyclic compounds have been reported [7-8]. Heterocyclic compounds provide a great synthetic and structural versatility due to their having a number of potential substitution positions.

Pyrazole has proven to be very efficient as starting materials for various kinds of mesogenic compounds. Terminal substitutions play a vital role in imparting liquid crystallinity to potentially mesogenic group like H, OH, I, Br, Cl, Me, OMe, OR and NO₂ occupy the p p' position of the central core. Some of these groups are highly polar and others mildly polar [9].

Five membered rings of the pyrazole have aromatic character [10], planer conformation and high dipole moments perpendicular to the principal molecular axis. Indeed, some 3, 5-disubstituted pyrazoles and 4-substituted pyrazole have demonstrated their ability to show liquid crystalline behavior both as themselves [11-12] and with metal co-ordination [13-14]. Purely organic mesogenic β -diketone derivatives have also been reported. Calamatic mesomorphism has also been described in a number of pyrazoles derived from 4-alkoxy substituted aromatic β -diketone [15-16]. These compounds exhibit classical nematic and smectic-A and C mesophases despite the fact that the type of mesophase depends on the nature and length of the terminal chain. It has been shown that the short chains give rise to rather narrow mesophase ranges or no mesophases at all; therefore, the intermediate and long chains are of great interest. In earlier study we described the preparation and mesomorphic study of pyrazolone derivative as terminal moiety [17].

Where, R = C_nH_{2n+1}; n = 7, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16 and 18

X = H; 4-[(4-*n*-alkoxyphenyl) (4-*n*-octyloxyphenylimino) methyl]-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazole-5(4*H*) one

Experimental:

Materials:

4-Hydroxy acetanilide and 4-hydroxybenzoic acid were obtained from Merck, Germany. Alkyl bromides (Lancaster, England), 5-methyl-2-phenyl-2,4-dihydro-3*H*-pyrazol-3-one and 5-methyl-2-(4-methylphenyl)-2,4-dihydro-3*H*-pyrazol (Nutan Dye Chem, Sachin-G.I.D.C.) was used without further purification. Thionyl chloride was made of Polypharm Mumbai. KOH, NaOH, anhydrous K₂CO₃, CaCl₂, acetone, ethanol, methanol, acetic acid, ethyl acetate, petroleum ether, diethyl ether, HCl, H₂SO₄, ammonia, etc., were used as received. Column chromatography was performed by Acme's Silica Gel (100–200 mesh). Solvents were dried and distilled prior to use.

Synthesis:**Preparation of 4-[(4-*n*-alkoxyphenyl)(4-*n*-octyloxyphenylimino)methyl]-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazole-5(4H)one****Synthesis of 4-*n*-alkoxy benzoic acid**

These were synthesized by alkylation of 4-hydroxy benzoic acid using the reported method of Gray and Jones [18-19].

Synthesis of 4-*n*-alkoxy benzoyl chlorides

These were synthesized of 4-hydroxy benzoyl chlorides using the reported method of Dave and Vora [20].

Synthesis of 4-(4-*n*-alkoxybenzoyl)-5-methyl-2-phenyl-2,4-dihydro-3H- pyrazol-3-one

The compound 4-(4-*n*-alkoxybenzoyl)-5-methyl-2-phenyl-2,4-dihydro-3H- pyrazol-3-one was prepared by condensation of 3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-5-ol and corresponding 4-*n*-alkoxy benzoyl chloride using Ca(OH)₂ as a catalyst as modified Jensen procedure [21]. In to a one liter three necked quick-fit flask containing dioxane (100ml), carrying a dropping funnel, a mechanical stirrer and a reflux condenser was placed 5-methyl-2-phenyl-2,4-dihydro-3H-pyrazol-3-one (0.098 mole, 17.07 g) A solution was obtained by gentle heating and stirring. Calcium hydroxide (0.14 mole, 10.0 g) was then added. The reaction mixture become paste. Corresponding 4-*n*-alkoxy benzoyl chloride (0.1 mole) mixed or dissolved in 50 mL of dioxane was then added drop wise. The reaction mixture was then refluxed with stirring for 2 hr. on a sand bath, during this period the bright yellow complex formed initially, turned yellowish brown. The complex was then decomposed by pouring the reaction mixture into chilled dil. HCl solution (500 ml, 3 N). A yellowish brown paste separated first, solidified after 2 to 3 minutes, was collected over a sintered glass funnel, washed with distilled water till the washings were colourless and dried in air. The desired compounds obtained were crystallized from ethanol.

Synthesis of 4-*n*-alkoxy aniline

These were synthesized by alkylation of 4-hydroxy acetanilide followed by hydrolysis using the reported method.[22-24]

Synthesis of 4-((4-methoxyphenyl)((4-(octyloxy)phenyl)imino)methyl)-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-5(4H)-one

A mixture of 1 mmol 4-(4-*n*-alkoxybenzoyl)-5-methyl-2-phenyl-2,4-dihydro-3H-pyrazol-3-one or 4-(4-*n*-alkoxybenzoyl)-5-methyl-2-(4-methylphenyl)-2,4-dihydro-3H-pyrazol-3-one, 1 mmol 4-*n*-octyloxy aniline and three drops of sulfuric acid in 10 ml of absolute ethanol was refluxed for 4 hrs. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool and was stirred at room temperature overnight. The solid was collected and recrystallized from ethanol several times Yield 82% [25-26].

Scheme**Step-I**

4-*n*-alkoxy benzoyl chloride
(Where R = C_nH_{2n+1}, n = 7, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18)

Step-III

X=H; 4-(4-*n*-alkoxybenzoyl)-5-methyl-2-phenyl-2,4-dihydro-3*H*-pyrazol-3-one

Step-IV

Step-V

Where, X=H; 4-[(4-*n*-alkoxyphenyl)(4-*n*-octyloxyphenylimino)methyl]-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazole-5-ol

Result and Discussion

In present study, 7 homologues from 4-(4-*n*-alkoxybenzoyl)-5-methyl-2-phenyl-2,4-dihydro-3*H*-pyrazol-3-one were synthesized and characterized. The characterization of the compounds has been done by elemental analyses. The physical data are listed in Table-1. The elemental analysis data are agreed with theoretical values as per expected structure. The characteristic IR- frequencies of the mesogenic compounds are given in Table-2 and the IR spectra of representative compounds are shown in Figure-1. ¹H-NMR spectral data of the representative compounds are given in Table-3 and their spectra shown in Figure-2. The DSC analysis data are given in Table-6 and Figer-5. The DSC data of compound E₁₀ were show Cr – SmA phase at 86 °C, SmA- N phase at 91 °C and N-I phase at 125 °C.

Table-1: Data table of the Elemental analysis

Comp.	Molecular Formula	Mol. Wt. g/mol	M.P. °C	% Yield	Color	Rf Value	Analysis (%), Found (Calculated)		
							C	H	N
E ₇	C ₃₈ H ₄₉ O ₃ N ₃	595	130	74	Brown	0.87	76.44(76.63)	8.11(8.23)	7.12(7.05)
E ₈	C ₃₉ H ₅₁ O ₃ N ₃	609	118	70	Brown	0.89	76.90(76.84)	8.20(8.37)	6.72(6.89)
E ₁₀	C ₄₁ H ₅₅ O ₃ N ₃	637	125	81	Brown	0.94	77.10(77.23)	8.49(8.63)	6.41(6.59)
E ₁₂	C ₄₃ H ₅₉ O ₃ N ₃	665	132	77	Brown	0.91	77.41(77.59)	8.71(8.87)	6.21(6.31)
E ₁₄	C ₄₅ H ₆₃ O ₃ N ₃	693	115	73	Brown	0.88	77.82(77.92)	8.91(9.09)	6.13(6.06)
E ₁₆	C ₄₇ H ₆₇ O ₃ N ₃	721	105	75	Brown	0.95	78.01(78.22)	9.11(9.29)	5.74(5.82)
E ₁₈	C ₄₉ H ₇₁ O ₃ N ₃	749	110	74	Brown	0.93	78.32(78.50)	9.21(9.47)	5.43(5.60)

Table-2: Characteristic IR absorption frequencies

Functional Group	Bond and it's mode of vibration	Intensity	Position of absorption (cm ⁻¹)
			E ₁₀
-CH ₃ , -CH ₂ (Aliphatic)	C-H (str.)	s	2853, 2925
-C=N (azomethine linkage)	C=N (str.)	m	1686
-C=O of pyrazolone (in keto form)	C=O (str.)	m	1717
-C=N (Pyrazolone)	C=N (str.)	s	1607
-C-N (pyrazolone)	C-N(str.)	s	1307
-C=C-	C=C (str.)	w	1579, 1469, 1432
-C-O of alkoxy chain	C-O (asym. str.)	s	1167
-C-O-C-	C-O-C (sym. str.)	s	1022
-C-O-C-	C-O-C (asym. str.)	s	1256
-(CH ₂) _n -	C-H (roc.)	m	718

Table-3: ¹H-NMR spectral data (δ ppm)

Code No.	-CH ₃ protons of aliphatic chain	-CH ₂ protons of aliphatic chain	-CH ₂ O protons of alkoxy chain	-CH protons of pyrazolone at 4-position	-CH ₃ attached to pyrazolone ring at 5-position	-CH ₃ of Substituted phenyl ring at 2-position on pyrazolone	Aromatic protons (m)
E ₁₀	0.865-0.896 (t)	1.274-1.474(m) 1.726-1.824(q)	3.983-4.037 (t)	3.883 (s)	2.174 (s)	-	6.886-8.061 (m)

Table-4: Electronic absorption spectral data

Compound	Molecular formula	Wavelength λ _{max} (nm)	Absorbance	Molar absorptivity ε x 10 ⁴
E ₇	C ₃₈ H ₄₉ O ₃ N ₃	259.00	1.230	12.30
E ₈	C ₃₉ H ₅₁ O ₃ N ₃	303.50 241.00	1.287 1.096	12.87 10.96
E ₁₀	C ₄₁ H ₅₅ O ₃ N ₃	258.00	1.234	12.34
E ₁₂	C ₄₃ H ₅₉ O ₃ N ₃	301.00	1.285	12.85
E ₁₄	C ₄₅ H ₆₃ O ₃ N ₃	260.00	1.159	11.59
E ₁₆	C ₄₇ H ₆₇ O ₃ N ₃	258.00	1.155	11.55
E ₁₈	C ₄₉ H ₇₁ O ₃ N ₃	303.00	1.280	12.80

Table-5: Transition temperature (°C) data

Code No.	R=C _n H _{2n+1} n=	Transition temperature in °C						
		Cr		Sm		N	I	
E ₇	7	•	-	•	101	•	130	•
E ₈	8	•	89	•	92	•	118	•
E ₁₀	10	•	86	•	91	•	125	•
E ₁₂	12	•	72	•	87	•	132	•
E ₁₄	14	•	70	•	90	•	115	•
E ₁₆	16	•	86	•	96	•	105	•
E ₁₈	18	•	79	•	-	•	110	•

(*)Monotropic phase

Table-6: Transition temperature and DSC data
4-(4-*n*-alkoxybenzoyl)-5-methyl-2-phenyl-2,4-dihydro-3H-pyrazol-3-one

Series	Code No.	Transition	Peak Temp. (Microscopic temp.) °C	ΔH Jg ⁻¹	ΔS Jg ⁻¹ k ⁻¹
		Cr-Sm	86.122(86)	21.459	0.0597
	E ₁₀	Sm-N	91.751(91)	7.431	0.0203
		N-I	125.811(125)	12.918	0.0323

Figure:1 FT-IR spectra of compound E-10

Figure: 2 ¹H-NMR spectra of compound E-10

Figure: 3 UV/Visible spectra

Figure: 4 Transition temperature curve

Figure: 5 DSC thermogram of compound E-10

(a)

(b)

Figure: 6 Smectic phase on cooling at 79°C (E₁₈), (b) Nematic droplets at 92°C on cooling (E₈),**Thermal and phase behavior**

The liquid crystalline phases of all the synthesized compounds were observed using a polarizing optical microscope (POM) attached with linkam hot stage. The thin-film samples were obtained by sandwiching them a glass slide and cover slip.

A droplet nematic phase was observed in the E₈ compound upon cooling at 92°C, which shows a Schlieren-like texture. This texture shows a fine thread-like pattern of dark and light areas, indicating the typical disordered but oriented structure of the nematic phase. Brush-shaped disclination lines are present in the Schlieren texture, confirming the nematic phase. The stability of this phase at 92°C indicates that E₈ behaves as a medium-temperature

nematic liquid crystal. The smectic-A phase was observed in the E₁₈ compound upon cooling to 79°C, which has a distinct fan-shaped texture. These fan-shaped domains are characteristic of the smectic-A phase, in which the molecules are arranged in a layered structure and within each layer the molecules are perpendicular to the layers. The fan-shaped texture develops from structures commonly known as “batonnets” and indicates a more ordered layered arrangement of the smectic-A phase. The presence of this phase at 79°C indicates that E₁₈ has medium-temperature smectic behavior.

Conclusion:

In this study, we have presented the synthesis and characterization of new mesogenic homologous series viz. 4-[(4-*n*-alkoxyphenyl)(4-*n*-octyloxyphenylimino)methyl]-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazole-5-ol which containing Schiff base central linkage with tri substituted pyrazole contain liquid crystals have been synthesized and characterized. The introduction of pyrazole with tri substituted unit in rigid core induced enantiotropic behavior.

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